

ENGLISH TEACHING METHODS AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Language teaching, like any other topic, has undergone a lot of changes. It has shifted to role-plays, interactive games, short visuals, etc. from the traditional ways, such as lectures by facilitators with only a blackboard to support and spell repetition and grammar worksheets, have shifted to role-plays.

Language teaching has its challenges. Most of the time, it is a foreign language that the learner can't pick up from his/her surroundings, and you should teach patiently and systematically so that the students become confident and can read, write and speak the language effortlessly.

The English language is the language of the world, and English teachers have changed their methods of delivery over the years to suit the present scenario. In this article, I will be discussing specific popular and efficient ways of teaching the English language, which fulfills the demand of modern learners.

Primary Methods of Teaching English

According to Asher and James (1982), "Methods are the combination of techniques that are used and plasticized by the teachers in the classrooms to teach their students and approaches are the philosophies of teachers about language teaching that can be applied in the classrooms by using different techniques of language teaching."

This method of teaching English is a classic one used since the 16th century. This approach was improvised for teaching the Latin language, which was not commonly learned and spoken by people. The method of teaching English focused on translating the texts in Latin to the native language and then gaining it, in line with the grammatical rules and vocabulary of Latin. The rote learning method is the most used method to learn vocabulary.

Later on, this method was used to learn other languages that were considered a second language. Thus, it applies to English as well. This approach lacks in the fact that it is not a very good way of teaching to communicate appropriately in English. Though this old-fashioned method has received a lot of criticism in

modern times, many institutions still use it, especially by those who want to study English scientifically.

Natural Method :

This method of teaching English, also known as the direct method, seems to be a response to the Grammar translation technique. In this process, the teacher who is aiming to teach English as a second language, asks the learner to think in English so that they can communicate in English.

The technique aims at building a connection between thought and expression. It required the teacher to strictly prohibit the student from using his/her native language. The learner is supposed to perfectly express himself/herself in English, with proper accent and usage of grammatical skills.

This method of teaching English is used in modern times and is useful in teaching to communicate in English. As the student thinks and talks in English in real-life situations, they learn the language accurately, and there is no rote learning or translation. This might take some time, but whatever is learned has a long term effect on our memory

Humanistic Approach :

During the 1970s, teaching and learning course underwent a radical change wherein the learner's innate potential and acquired skills were the focal point of the education process. A few teaching methods were devised based on this idea, and these were grouped under the title of the humanistic approach. Some of the Methods of Teaching English under the humanistic approaches are:

Suggestopedia:

This method of teaching English is based on the fact that the mind has great potential and can memorize information by suggestions. This method uses certain principles of memory to teach English as a second language.

The learners are provided with chunks of new information in the original language (English in our case), and it is read aloud with classical music in its background. This activity is known as a concert reading. The idea of suggestopedia is to provide a relaxed atmosphere for the mind to learn and retain that information. This method is useful if the learner is shy or apprehensive. The supporters of this technique include Georgi Lozanov, whose methods have become Accelerated Learning Movement.

Silent Way:

This method of teaching English, also known as the Natural approach, is based on the idea of how human beings learn to speak their mother tongue. Caleb Gattegno devised this method of language teaching. According to him, the

teacher should be silent as much as possible, but the students should be motivated to speak the language. The silent way method uses elements such as color charts and the colored Cuisenaire rods, etc. Certain principles on which this method is based are: Learning happens when the learner learns to discover new things about the foreign language and is creative rather than repeating what is taught. Learning is encouraged by physical objects in the surrounding. It is based on problem-solving. This method of teaching English is perfect for beginners or young learners of English.

Total Physical Response:

This method involves acting out language rather than speaking. It can be through mimicry or only responding to audiovisual cues. Games like 'Simon says...' or the charades are classic examples of this method of teaching. This method is a fun way of learning language and therefore is very useful.

Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL)

This method applies to schools where most of the important subjects are taught in English. This is prevalent in modern classrooms. The focus is on the content, and the lessons are tailored to suit the student's needs and preferences. CLIL is effective in teaching students the real-life application of the English language as a means of expressing culturally.

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